

D5.1 Development of computational framework for non-invasive parameterization of physics-based models

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Executive Summary

The main objective of the deliverable D5.1 is the description of the computational framework, which enables the direct extraction of physical parameters from experimental sequences, that will be formulated and optimized in T5.2. The aim of this work is to follow a non-invasive approach to reduce the need of costly cell tear-down and avoid combinations of measurement techniques which lack compatibility and which require sophisticated devices and knowledge how to interpret and analysis the complex data.

To achieve this, in DigiBatt we follow an inverse modelling approach as the essential technique for parameter extraction. This means, the developed framework fits the model to the experimental data to obtain the desired parameters. So far, a variety of basic optimisation algorithms are available, for which applicability is granted in the PyBOP software, an open source framework developed by DigiBatt partner UOXF for said purpose. We investigated the structure of this software and decided to use this as the underlying computational framework, as it is easily accessible and extendable, and transparent in its functionality. Despite the already implemented basic algorithms we further investigated the application of Bayesian algorithms, since they have the potential to tackle well-known parameterization problems, e.g., uncertainty and unique identifiability. We showed that the Bayesian approach is able to resolve these problems in parallel to the main parameterization task, giving further information on the performed parameterization. Therefore, the basic Bayesian algorithm, EP-BOLFI, was further developed, leading to the tools SOBER and BASQ as parallelizable improvements. We plan to implement these tools into the PyBOP framework which should then act as the computational toolbox to analyse the data from future experimental tasks in the project. To condense the variety of algorithms, we plan to perform a benchmarking of the tools by applying them to different orders of complexity in the experimental data. This will be extended to include parameterization of Electrochemical Thermal Coupling Models which follows an approach that combines Artificial Intelligence, model and data to compete with large datasets. Since the different patches of the computational framework, e.g., forward simulating models and inverse modelling routines, start to show the working functionality, the linking of these patches becomes essential for an automated workflow. With this scope we have implemented automated parameter usage and linking using ontologies particularly developed for use in battery research.

To conclude, we have set up the main structure of the computational framework to achieve the parameterization of models for different applications in battery research. As the main gears inside the framework, we looked into various optimisers, showed their functionality and the upsides of utilizing Bayesian algorithms. To link the several components of the framework an automatable solution based on ontologies has been

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established as central piece to facilitate the overall objective to accelerate battery testing via increasing the value and efficiency of battery models. While still being subject to further optimization and integration, the development of the computational framework for non-invasive parameter extraction is largely finished and awaits its application to experimental sequences. Their design and execution are from now on the main working focus.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
WP	Work package
EB	Executive Board
GA	General Assembly
AB	Advisory Board
EP	Expectation Propagation
BO	Bayesian Optimization
LFI	Likelihood Free Inference
PyBOP	Python Battery Optimisation and Parameterisation
PyBaMM	Python Battery Mathematical Modelling
SoC	State of Charge
SEI	Solid-Electrolyte Interphase
BQ	Bayesian Quadrature
SOBER	Solving Optimisation as Bayesian Estimation via Recombination
BASQ	Bayesian Alternate Subsampled Quadrature
EIS	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
DRT	Distribution of Relaxation Times
ECTM	Electrochemical Thermal Coupling Model
AI	Artificial Intelligence

1. Introduction to parameterization

To describe, understand and predict real-world systems, researchers make use of physically derived models that describe the different processes taking place. These models usually depend on a multitude of parameters which have to be determined correctly to obtain a model which is consistent with experimental observations. The parameter set includes microstructural, thermal, thermodynamic, kinetic and transport parameters for which comprehensive characterization on material-, component- (electrodes, electrolyte and separator) and cell-level is required. Often, many of the model parameters cannot be measured or are only indirectly observable, especially if one is limited to non-invasive methods. For highly complex systems like batteries, which exhibit non-linear behaviours across multiple scales and are sensitive to a wide array of variables, the parameterization task is analytically unsolvable and becomes even numerically very challenging. The complicated nature of batteries shapes this parameterization as an ill-posed problem.

Inverse modelling is a powerful approach to overcome the ill-posed problem as it works backward from the observed data. Instead of starting with known parameters to simulate outputs, inverse modelling involves comparing observed system behaviour with model predictions and adjusting parameters to minimize resulting discrepancies. Even though there are many algorithms that execute the parameterization using inverse modelling, they share a very similar internal structure to build upon. First, a certain preliminary belief about the parameters is needed: the search space. Depending on the numbers of parameters this space can be high-dimensional. Second, a sampling function is used that outputs different points in the parameter space, depending on previously drawn samples and obtained information. Third, a forward model is utilized that takes the sampled parameter combinations as input and simulates a given experimental sequence. The output consists then of the quantity of interest, which should be compared to the experimental observation. Fourth, the cost function which specifies how the comparison between simulated and experimental data is carried out. It acts as evaluation metric and yields the discrepancy (or loss) which is linked to the simulated point in parameter space. Simulating multiple parameter combinations gives a high-dimensional loss-landscape which contains the information about valid parameters. Optimising the discrepancy is equal to finding the minimum in this loss-landscape. A global minimum represents the best parameter configuration for a given combination of model, data and cost function.

Since the parameters in the type of electrochemical, degradation and thermal models that we describe herein possess clear physical meanings, it is critical to ensure their values remain physically plausible. To achieve this, where it makes sense, parameter boundary values will be determined through an extensive literature review. Specifically, the review will focus on studies involving batteries with similar materials, summarizing the reported parameter ranges as reference boundaries for parameter identification.

This approach ensures consistency with the battery's material properties and maintains the physical validity of the models.

Given the large number of parameters and their varying impacts on the model's voltage and temperature outputs, a sensitivity analysis prior to the parameterization is of high value. This analysis will evaluate the identifiability of the parameters and quantify their influence on model behavior. The outcomes of the sensitivity analysis will serve as a guide for:

- Selecting the most informative data for parameterization.
- Designing an efficient parameter identification framework.

The variety of existent inverse modelling algorithms originates from the flexibility of how to address the above-mentioned pillars of the inverse technique. By that, the different algorithms have quite different advantages and performance depending on the specific application. In the following we describe the computational framework that we plan to use and establish in the frame of the project. Further, we shortly summarize the computational resources regarding the executions of forward models, as a substantial part of the parameter extraction. In chapter four, we describe Bayesian optimizers, a family of inverse algorithms using Bayesian principles with substantial advantages for parameter extraction. Subsequently, we look at extracting parameters that describe the thermal coupling in batteries. Finally, we elaborate on the digital solutions for automating the parameter usage and link the different aspects.

2. The Computational Framework: PyBOP

PyBOP (Python Battery Optimisation and Parameterisation) is a versatile computational open source framework designed for parameterisation and optimisation of battery models and developed by DigiBatt partner UOXF. It provides a robust set of tools for both point-based and distribution-based parameter identification, offering flexibility to the battery researchers. By providing numerous example workflows, PyBOP ensures a smooth user experience, helping users navigate the complexities of battery model parameterisation [7].

Figure 1 Scheme of how PyBOP integrates into the design and optimisation workflow and interacts with complementary software tools.

2.1 Key Applications

PyBOP has two primary applications:

1. **Parameter Inference from Battery Test Data:** The framework allows users to infer model parameters from experimental data, providing a detailed understanding of battery behavior.
2. **Constrained Design Optimisation:** PyBOP facilitates optimisation tasks related to battery design, considering various manufacturing and operational constraints. These tasks encompass a range of challenges, from selecting appropriate battery models to choosing suitable design parameters.

While the second application is very interesting for cell and component development activities, in DigiBatt we are focusing on the first application as it offers the possibility to parameterize battery models from electrochemical measurements.

2.2 Supported Models, Algorithms, and Cost Functions:

PyBOP supports a wide array of battery models, optimisation algorithms, and cost functions, offering a high degree of adaptability for diverse research needs. A summary of the currently supported features is provided below:

Table 1 Overview of battery models, optimisation algorithms, and cost functions available in PyBOP. They are compatible in any combination, regardless of row.

Battery Models	Optimisation Algorithms	Cost Functions
Single Particle Model (SPM)	Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES)	Sum of Squared Errors (SSE)
Single Particle Model with Electrolyte (SPMe)	Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)	Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)
Doyle-Fuller-Newman (DFN)	Exponential Natural Evolution Strategy (xNES)	Minkowski
Many Particle Model (MPM)	Separable Natural Evolution Strategy (sNES)	Sum of Power
Multi-Species Multi-Reaction (MSMR)	Adaptive Moment Estimation with Weight Decay (AdamW)	Gaussian Log Likelihood
Weppner-Huggins	Improved Resilient Backpropagation (iRProp-)	Log Posterior
Equivalent Circuit Models (ECM)	SciPy Minimize & Differential Evolution	Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF)
	Cuckoo Search	Gravimetric Energy Density
	Gradient Descent	Volumetric Energy Density
	Nelder-Mead	

2.3 Integration with PyBaMM

One of PyBOP's key features is its seamless compatibility with the PyBaMM (Python Battery Mathematical Modelling) framework which is an open source battery modelling tool frequently used in the battery community, available at <https://github.com/pybamm-team/PyBaMM>. This integration enables users to parameterise a variety of battery models, ranging from electrochemical models like the Doyle-Fuller-Newman model to simpler equivalent circuit models. PyBaMM can easily simulate a variety of measurement protocols with any of its models: cycling, rate tests, Galvanostatic Intermittent Titration Technique (GITT), or Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements, to name a few. See Table 1 for a complete list of models in PyBaMM. The electrochemical models may be extended with already implemented models for degradation phenomena and thermal effects, which are not listed in Table 1. These include, but are not limited to: Solid Electrolyte Interphase growth and mechanics, particle cracking, loss of active material, porosity changes, or lithium plating.

2.4 Practical Implications

The wide array of supported methods allows PyBOP to address a diverse range of parameterisation and optimisation problems. Whether dealing with complex design requirements, or the selection of appropriate cost functions, PyBOP provides the necessary tools to tackle these challenges. This makes it a vital resource for advancing battery technology, from deriving a better understanding of limiting processes in cells, to improving cell performance and optimising energy density.

For further details and to access the framework, visit the PyBOP GitHub repository: <https://github.com/pybop-team/PyBOP>. The example notebook files can be found here: <https://nbviewer.org/github/pybop-team/PyBOP/tree/develop/examples/notebooks/>.

3. Linked Data for automating parameter usage

Parameter sets for physical modelling of batteries often include a combination of structural parameters - such as electrode thickness, particle size - and material parameters like diffusion coefficients, and conductivities. However, they are frequently scattered across various formats and repositories, leading to inconsistencies, inefficiencies, and challenges in reproducibility. The Battery Interface Ontology (BattINFO) addresses these issues by providing a unified semantic foundation that connects parameters to their associated models, experimental data, and material characterizations. This facilitates the management and utilization of battery model parameter sets, which are critical for accurate simulations and the development of digital twins.

By standardizing how parameters are defined and represented, BattINFO provides a foundation to improve the machine-readability of parameter sets. This is an essential step towards supporting automation. The ontology uses a shared vocabulary and explicit relationships to ensure that are described with clear, unambiguous meanings and consistent units. This standardization eliminates the ambiguity that often arises in manual parameter management and supports seamless integration across different modelling tools.

The ontology also promotes interoperability by linking parameter sets to their provenance, such as the specific experiments or materials from which they were derived. This makes it possible to automate workflows where parameter sets are retrieved and applied to models based on defined criteria. For example, a simulation tool can query the ontology to find parameters relevant to a specific battery chemistry and operating conditions, enabling efficient model setup. By automating these processes, the BattINFO ontology reduces the reliance on manual intervention, saving time and minimizing the potential for errors.

The ontology also supports the creation of linked data libraries of parameter sets. These libraries can serve as repositories for validated parameters that are easily accessible for reuse in different modelling scenarios.

The BattINFO ontology streamlines the management and application of battery model parameter sets. By providing a robust semantic framework, it enhances the machine-readability, interoperability, and reproducibility of battery modelling activities. This provides a foundation for creating automated battery data processing workflows, which is essential to fully utilize all of the battery data generated through research and innovation activities.

To access BattINFO for development purposes, please visit <https://github.com/BIG-MAP/BattINFO>. If you wish to use it in production, please make yourself familiar with the tutorial: <https://big-map.github.io/BattINFO/pages/getstarted.html>.

4. Overview of Bayesian Optimizers within DigiBatt

As outlined above, the result of the inverse parameterisation yields a best parameter configuration depending on model, data and cost-function. In real-world applications data is always accompanied by noise and uncertainty. The same accounts for the modelling part. Even if the forward models are derived from physical principles, various assumptions or numerical simplifications were made. Thereby, it is also not certain that the underlying model is the correct descriptor for a specific process. In highly complex and coupled systems as batteries, the interplay of physical processes is inevitable, impeding isolated parameterisation and question independent parameter identifiability. All of these difficulties shape the parameterisation of battery models as a non-deterministic exercise which is accompanied with uncertainty. Bayesian optimisers tackle these issues by intrinsically handling the optimization as a probabilistic task. In that manner the Bayesian principle

$$P(\theta|y) \sim P(y|\theta)P(\theta)$$

is used, where the prior belief $P(\theta)$ of the parameters is updated with the likelihood for the corresponding data $P(y|\theta)$, to obtain the posterior distribution $P(\theta|y)$ of the parameters. The obtained multidimensional probability directly addresses the main issues of the parameterization process. The point in parameter space with the highest likelihood can be considered as the best parameter configuration. The width or variance of the distribution around this value contains the information about the uncertainty in the result. The shape of the multidimensional probability distribution covers the correlation between different parameters, encoding the uniqueness of the parameterization and together with the uncertainty the general parameter identifiability.

In the following we present different Bayesian algorithms for inverse parameterization that will be used in the future of the project to parameterize the digital twins. These will also be incorporated into PyBOP as the underlying computational framework for these optimisers.

4.1 EP-BOLFI

The main work done within DigiBatt regarding EP-BOLFI [1] has been published recently in detail by Philipp et al. [2]. Here we shortly summarize the main functionality and new results achieved within the DigiBatt project.

4.1.1 Description

EP-BOLFI is a Bayesian Optimization (BO) algorithm which combines the classical optimization scheme with a special way of information propagation. EP in EP-BOLFI refers to Expectation Propagation. This is a technique to "divide and conquer" high-dimensional cost functions into more tractable portions. By specific data transformations, the fitting task is divided into characteristic features. Each feature is optimized for at once, and the gained knowledge is then propagated to the optimization of the next feature.

BOLFI in EP-BOLFI refers to Bayesian Optimization for Likelihood-Free Inference (LFI). This is a technique to enable black-box optimization under uncertainty. By utilizing an LFI transformation on model-data distance evaluations, it calculates a Likelihood instead of a pre-computed statistical model.

In an iterative routine feature by feature is inversely modelled yielding a converging probability distribution as result. In the following we show how this algorithm is used for optimization and whether it addresses the main problems of parameter extraction for battery models. As we have shown in previous work under the BIG-MAP project the parameterization with this algorithm works reliably for synthetic and real data. We elaborate here on further problematic aspects of parameterization.

To access EP-BOLFI, please visit the EP-BOLFI GitHub repository at <https://github.com/YannickNoelStephanKuhn/EP-BOLFI> and make yourself familiar with the examples: <https://github.com/YannickNoelStephanKuhn/EP-BOLFI/tree/main/examples>.

4.1.2 Application

- 1. Example:** As first example we utilize EP-BOLFI to inversely model synthetic battery degradation during storage by Solid-Electrolyte-Interphase (SEI) growth. The SEI is a passivating layer which grows on the negative electrode by ongoing reduction reactions of electrolyte molecules, consuming Li-ions and thereby lowering the cell capacity over time. The literature proposes several transport mechanisms which can drive the SEI growth. In this particular example we model the SEI growth by a superposition of solvent and electron diffusion, resulting in a net electron current density for SEI growth:

$$j_{SEI} = \frac{c_e - D_e - F}{L_{SEI}} \exp\left(\frac{FU(SoC)}{RT}\right) + \frac{c_s D_s F}{L_{SEI}},$$

with L_{SEI} the thickness of the SEI, F the Faraday constant, R the universal gas constant, T the temperature, the open-circuit potential $U(SoC)$ which depends on the state-of-charge (SoC), the concentrations c_x of lithium interstitials or electrolyte, and the diffusion constant D_x of lithium interstitials or the electrolyte. Especially in this example we look at the unique parameter identifiability.

Therefore, the parameters of interest are c_{e^-} , D_{e^-} , c_S , and D_S . As can be seen these appear only as direct products making them non-identifiable. The correlations of the resulting posterior distribution for the found parameters are shown in Fig. 2. It clearly indicates that in this setup the parameter pairs cannot be distinguished which corresponds to a correlation coefficient of $\rho(c_X|D_X) \approx -1$ in the overall posterior and in the chosen features. By that we know that it is not meaningful to parameterize these parameters individual, and they can only be optimized in a grouped description.

Figure 2 Pearson-correlation coefficients for inverse modelling the synthetic storage data while optimising the parameters c_{e^-} , D_{e^-} , c_S , and D_S . Each matrix contains the correlation coefficients from the probability distribution received by optimizing the individual feature or condensed in the resulting overall posterior.

2. Example: For the second example we inversely model synthetic data of capacity loss due to SEI growth during cycling. The modeled SEI electron current density is a superposition of solvent diffusion, electron diffusion and electron migration:

$$j_{SEI} = \frac{c_{e^-} D_{e^-} F}{L_{SEI}} \exp\left(\frac{FU(SoC)}{RT}\right) + \frac{c_S D_S F}{L_{SEI}} + \frac{c_{e^-} D_{e^-} F^2}{2RT\kappa_{SEI}} j_{int} \exp(-\eta_{SEI}(U(SoC))),$$

where κ_{SEI} is the Li-ion conductivity of the SEI, j_{int} is the intercalation current density and η_{SEI} is the SEI overpotential. The parameters of interest are then D_{e^-} , D_{EC} , and κ_{SEI} . Doing this for synthetic data lets us control the applied noise level. Looking at different noise levels and comparing the obtained parameter variances gives insight whether the resulting uncertainty in the parameterization captures the uncertainty in the data. In Tab. 2 one can see that the resulting variances indeed decrease with lower or vanishing noise.

Table 2 Non-dimensional posterior variances after 6864 simulated samples. The variances are given in logarithmic scale, i.e., the standard deviation measure the width of the distribution in e-folds.

Variances	$\sigma_{noise}^2 = 8 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{Ah}^2$	$\sigma_{noise}^2 = 8 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{Ah}^2$
$\sigma_{D_{e^-}}^2$	0.01	0.08
$\sigma_{D_S}^2$	0.24	0.45
$\sigma_{\kappa_{SEI}}^2$	0.02	0.13

A further important aspect of the parameterization example is the influence of the cost-function on the result. In terms of EP-BOLFI the cost function is realized by the chosen feature-transformation f_i , as it is used to measure the discrepancy between simulation and experimental observation:

$$discrepancy \sim ||f_i(y_{sim}(\theta)) - f_i(y_{exp})||.$$

To test the influence of the cost-function we chose two different features. First, we use directly the data points as features, which will result in the typical minimization of the squares. Second, we transform the data by fitting a power-law ($y \sim \alpha t^\beta$) to the data and then use the coefficients α and β for comparison. In Fig. 3 the two-dimensional landscape ($D_{e^-} - D_S$ plane, at the correct value of κ_{SEI}) of the loss-function for the different features is shown. The rows correspond to different noise levels. In the case of vanishing noise both features find a global minimum for the correct parameter combination (red dot). In the case of the data point feature one can recognize a sharp valley of low discrepancies. For higher noise values the landscape changes and indicates no longer a global minimum for the data point feature. Further, one can see that the width of the valley increases, which visualizes the uncertainty. The shape of the valley contains the information about the parameter correlation which depends also on the chosen feature and the location in parameter space. By that we confirm, that a suitable feature-choice has high impact on the correct parameter identification, the resulting uncertainty and the overall algorithmic performance.

Figure 3 Loss-landscape of two-dimensional parameter space for different features (columns) and different noise levels (top row: $\sigma_{noise}^2 = 0 \text{Ah}^2$, bottom row: $\sigma_{noise}^2 = 8 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{Ah}^2$). The color indicates the discrepancy of the simulated data to the experimental observation which is calculated as $L = \log \left(\left| \frac{f_i(y_{sim}(\theta))}{f_i(y_{exp})} - 1 \right| \right)$.

4.2 SOBER

4.2.1 Description

SOBER is a Bayesian Optimization (BO) and Bayesian Quadrature (BQ) algorithm. Since the BQ part of SOBER is published under its own name, BASQ, we describe it in detail under that name. SOBER is designed to extend the general sample-efficiency of BO algorithms to massively parallelized computations, for instance, on graphics cards. Where EP-BOLFI is intentionally restrained to one sample at a time for the absolute maximum in sample efficiency, SOBER retains enough of that efficiency such that the computation time increases, but the wall-clock time decreases. Since pretty much all PCs now have at least four threads for computation, that trade-off is always favourable except in the case where you would like to run many parameterizations in parallel.

The mathematical foundation by which SOBER unlocks efficient parallel BO is an equivalent reformulation of the usual acquisition function optimization. Instead of the direct non-convex optimization that EP-BOLFI solves, SOBER transforms it into a kernel recombination task first, which can be solved with convex optimization. In practice,

SOBER can handle batch sizes in the thousands and efficiently explore combinatorically complex discrete model parameters. SOBER does all of this while remaining a global optimizer, as compared to previous solutions like Thompson Sampling, which tend to overexploit local optima.

Within DigiBatt, we extended SOBER with the EP and BOLFI capabilities of EP-BOLFI, making SOBER its definitive version. To access SOBER, please visit its GitHub repository at <https://github.com/ma921/SOBER/> and make yourself familiar with the tutorials: <https://github.com/ma921/SOBER/tree/main/tutorials>.

4.2.2 Application

SOBER can give a more nuanced insight into parameter cross-correlations. As an example, we inversely model impedance data with the Doyle-Fuller-Newman model. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) separates processes on multiple time scales clearly from each other, especially if the timescales range over multiple orders of magnitude. EIS, as any other battery measurement, is greatly afflicted by noise. As an example, we see an impedance measurement on a LG MJ1 cell anode in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Nyquist plot of impedance data from a LG MJ1 cell. While the noise in the high-frequency limit is obvious, it is also challenging to get consistent results for the low-frequency limit.

To discern between actual measurement features and noise, the technique Distribution of Relaxation Times (DRT) has gained attention recently. DRT transforms an impedance measurement into a continuous sum of RC elements, which would show up as semicircles in the Nyquist plot above. In Figure 5, we see the same measurement as in Figure 4, but in DRT format. Note that the DRT transform is lossy.

Figure 5 DRT plot of impedance data from a LG MJ1 cell. The parameters for the simulation are not fitted.

Using the double logarithmic view of the DRT, we can use the distance between measurement and simulation in it as a cost function for impedance model fitting. We now have everything we need to use SOBER: a model, data, and a cost function. All further implementation details are transparently available for fine-tuning within SOBER, but not necessary for our example.

With SOBER on its own, we only have access to the best observed parameter set. To analyse the results implicitly contained within the final state of a SOBER parameterization, we need BASQ.

4.3 BASQ

4.3.1 Description

BASQ is the Bayesian Quadrature (BQ) algorithm within SOBER. BQ algorithms are suited to broadly evaluate physics-based model properties over a range of model parameters. BASQ enables the reasonable computation of the so-called Evidence. The Evidence is the normalization factor present in the Bayesian Theorem. In a simplified manner, since larger Likelihoods require a larger Evidence to balance out the equation, better model fits have a higher Evidence. Another interpretation of the Evidence is that of the sharpness of the model parameter prediction. For that interpretation, we need to view the Evidence as a probability distribution itself, with a mean and a variance. The mean describes the

model fit quality. The variance describes the model fit uncertainty. So sharper predictions will have a smaller Evidence variance.

To access BASQ, please use it via its SOBER implementation at <https://github.com/ma921/SOBER/> where you will find BASQ itself at <https://github.com/ma921/SOBER/tree/main/SOBER/BASQ>. While there is a separate GitHub repository for BASQ at <https://github.com/ma921/BASQ>, consider it the deprecated version in favour of its SOBER implementation.

4.3.2 Application

BASQ can reduce the nuanced insights from SOBER back to comparable numbers. It also serves as evaluator of the Posterior SOBER produces. As that Posterior is a Gaussian Process with multiple warping layers and an underlying kernel density estimate of the training data, it is not necessarily interpretable itself. With BASQ, we can query it back into a probability density function over the range of model parameters, which also allows us to view the predictive posterior distribution by simulating the model on posterior evaluations. In Figure 6, we visualize the posterior approximation BASQ provides. In Figure 7, we visualize what is called the predictive posterior: model evaluations on samples taken from the posterior approximation in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Pairwise correlation plot of the posterior distribution of an impedance model fit; parameters in order of 0 to 5 are positive particle diffusivity, positive electrode exchange-current density, positive

electrode double-layer capacity, positive electrode Bruggeman coefficient, cation transference number, and thermodynamic factor.

Figure 7 Predictive posterior distribution of an impedance model fit. For demonstration purposes, this is a non-converged fit. Lighter shaded curves correspond to weaker Likelihoods.

As an example, we use BASQ as a model selection criterion based on the computed mean model evidence achieved by inversely analysing data with a certain model. In this example real degradation data of a battery during storage is simulated with different combinations of SEI growth transport mechanisms. As one can see in Fig. 8, both combinations describe a similar trend in the data. Using the model evaluations one obtains a scalar value for the mean model evidence, the higher the mean model evidence, the better the model is able to describe the data. From this one can consistently decide which model fits best to the data (see Tab. 3). To avoid overfitted models we investigated the possibility of introducing a penalty term into the likelihood of a parameter combination. The penalty depends on the number of parameters and lowers the model evidence of a model with more parameters, in case it does not fit the data reasonably better. This penalty was calibrated using synthetic data.

Figure 8 Inverse modelling of degradation data with different combinations of SEI growth mechanisms. Results obtained by EP-BOLFI.

Table 3 Mean model evidence computed by BASQ for different models (the higher the evidence the better). To avoid overfitted models achieving the highest model evidence, a penalty term depending on the number of used parameters is introduced into the likelihood.

Model	Real Data	Real Data + Penalty
Electron Diffusion + Solvent Diffusion	2.14	-9.12
Electron Conduction + Solvent Diffusion	-282.19	-291.42
Electron Diffusion + Electron Conduction + Solvent Diffusion	3.95	-13.13

5. Outlook: Thermal Parameter Extraction

So far, we have considered electrochemical and degradation models to demonstrate the applicability of the inverse modelling approach and the use of the reported frameworks. In the frame of DigiBatt, another data-driven parameterization framework based on artificial intelligence will be used, primarily focusing on the extraction of thermal parameters which will be described in the following. Naturally, the approach is not constraint to such a use-case but has already been employed for parameterization of an electrochemical model in the past as well [6] and will be included in the benchmark of the utilized frameworks within DigiBatt.

The performance of lithium-ion batteries is significantly affected by temperature. Therefore, it is necessary to couple an electrochemical model with a thermal model to obtain an Electrochemical Thermal Coupling Model (ECTM) that can accurately simulate the terminal voltage and temperature of the battery at the same time. The sources of heat generation during battery operation include electrochemical reactions, entropy changes associated with changes in the lattice structure of the active material, and the transport of electrons and ions. In addition, the battery will also exchange heat with the external environment, which will lead to a change in the battery temperature. Changes in the battery temperature will, in turn affect temperature-dependent parameters of the electrochemical model, including reaction rates, liquid phase diffusion, liquid phase electrical conductivity, and solid phase diffusion coefficients, which can be described using the Arrhenius equation:

$$X = X_{ref} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E_{\Lambda,X}}{R}\left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right)$$

where X stands for each of the temperature-dependent parameters. This equation determines the value of X at temperature T using the corresponding activation energy $E_{\Lambda,X}$, and the reference value X_{ref} at the reference temperature T_{ref} , with R being the universal gas constant.

Parameterization of ECTMs poses a particularly significant challenge due to the large number of parameters with distinct physical meaning. Experimental measurement of these parameters is often costly, time-consuming, and, in some cases, destructive. To address these limitations, this work proposes the development of a data-driven parameterization framework that integrates artificial intelligence with voltage and temperature data obtained through non-intrusive measurements. This approach aims to parameterize ECTMs effectively, reducing the reliance on expensive and destructive experimental methods. The reliability of data-driven parameterization methods is highly dependent on the quality of the input data. To ensure robustness, batteries must be tested under a wide range of operating conditions within their allowable temperature range. This ensures the collection of comprehensive current, voltage, and temperature

data, reflecting the battery's behavior at different temperatures. The collected dataset will be divided into two parts: (1) A subset for parameterizing the ECTM. (2) A subset for validating the parameterized model to demonstrate the reliability and accuracy of the results.

Finally, the framework for parameter identification combining the ECTM, AI, and experimental data is illustrated in figure 9. In DigiBatt, artificial intelligence algorithms, such as Bayesian optimization or the cuckoo search algorithm, will be further developed to parameterize the model quickly and accurately. These AI algorithms will generate candidate parameter sets for the ECTM. Experimentally measured current data will be input into the model, and the simulated voltage and temperature outputs will be compared against the measured voltage and temperature data. Based on the resulting error, the algorithm will refine the candidate parameter sets and propose improved ones. This iterative process will continue until an accurate ECTM is obtained.

Figure 9 Framework for data-driven parameterization of electrochemical thermal coupling models with artificial intelligence.

To further improve the accuracy of the results, the above framework can be developed into a multi-step, multi-objective parameter identification framework. Multi-step means that parameters can be identified in groups using different operating profiles. Multi-objective means that the objective function can be the voltage error, the temperature error, or the sum of the two under different operating conditions. Parameter identifiability varies under different operating conditions. Therefore, selecting appropriate data and establishing an appropriate parameter identification framework, combined with the results of sensitivity analysis, is crucial for efficient and accurate parameterization of ECTMs.

6. Conclusion

The parameterization of physics-based battery models is challenging and time-consuming as it usually involves the tear-down of cells and a large number of experiments on material-, electrode- and cell-level with different and highly specialized devices. To minimize the effort and required resources, we are focusing in DigiBatt on a non-invasive approach that requires mainly electrochemical data as input. Inverse modelling is a powerful technique that is able to handle the ill-posed parameterization task. We have shown that several digital tools exist within the DigiBatt consortium that can contribute to a more efficient parameter extraction by performing inverse modelling. As these tools have individual advantages depending on the complexity of the experimental sequence and the physical model description, it is highly preferred to have a complete toolbox available rather than restricting oneself to a single tool used for all applications. Therefore, we chose PyBOP as the computational framework which acts as such toolbox for various optimisers. Despite the already available optimisers we plan to extend this list by Bayesian optimisers investigated within DigiBatt.

As the parameterization is a non-deterministic task, we will primarily investigate Bayesian optimisers like EP-BOLFI, SOBER, and BASQ, which tackle the critical aspects as uncertainty quantification, parameter identifiability and model selection intrinsically. We showed that these Bayesian optimisers are able to detect indistinguishable parameter groups by the resulting correlation coefficients, which are calculated based on the covariances of the multidimensional probability distribution. Furthermore, we already investigated the obtained uncertainty of the inverse modelling routine by applying different noise levels to the analysed data. We were able to show that the uncertainty in the data is captured by the resulting variances of the optimised parameters. As a completion we looked also on the impact of the chosen cost-function, which evaluates the discrepancy between simulation and experiment. We could emphasize that a suitable feature transformation as cost-function can significantly improve the algorithmic performance regarding correct parameter-estimation, obtained uncertainty and convergence speed. Based on the promising results of the Bayesian approach, SOBER has been developed, which enables parallel Bayesian Optimization. To analyse the whole probability object achieved during the inverse modelling with SOBER, BASQ is needed. This algorithm handles the evidence calculation which quantifies the quality of the model-data fit. We have used this approach as a consistent model selection criterion in case multiple models describe similar trends in the data. As an outlook, we also describe the planned approach for the extraction of thermal parameters which are of major importance, since thermal changes in the battery during operation significantly influence the battery's performance and degradation. The presented approach is based on a combination of ECTMs, AI and experimental data, and will offer an additional option to the parameterization toolbox developed in the project.

Ultimately, with the multitude of available tools, it is necessary to thoroughly compare these and benchmark them on different scenarios and conditions, respectively. Therefore, we are currently setting up a benchmarking plan including the available optimisers. The aim is to estimate their performance and finally condense the number of used tools and required experiments to a needed minimum. This analysis will start with a synthetic dataset produced from an already parameterized battery model, i.e. with already known parameters from a fully characterized cell at high accuracy. This dataset will be gradually brought closer to resembling real data by inclusion of distinct levels of noise, before different sets of experimental data will be used. This includes already available data which has been shown to be successfully integrated in the workflow in the past as well as new data from the reference cell used in DigiBatt. During this collaborative experimental-computational work, besides assessing data quality, we will also start to investigate the effect of the experimental conditions and the exact procedures on the outcome and use the obtained knowledge to optimize workflows and procedures.

Importantly, automated workflows for data management and analysis as well as the exchange between experimentalists and theoreticians will be established in parallel. This is crucial as for the goal of accelerated battery research, the intersection of the different tools becomes substantial. With BATTInfo we showed the automated battery parameter usage, connecting the different working but yet isolated islands of computational framework, battery forward models and battery parameter extraction.

All in all, the computational framework and tools to use within this work-package are mostly set up. In future work these have to be brought together under the umbrella of PyBOP and benchmarked to focus on the most promising tools. The linking of the different tools is achieved using ontologies. With that the computational part of the task is complete, moving the focus to the experimental investigations which will be described in the upcoming deliverable report on experimental workflows for parameterizing physical models.

7. References and Links

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Links to the described tools and frameworks:

- PyBOP: <https://github.com/pybop-team/PyBOP>
- PyBaMM: <https://github.com/pybamm-team/PyBaMM>
- EP-BOLFI: <https://github.com/YannickNoelStephanKuhn/EP-BOLFI>
- SOBER: <https://github.com/ma921/SOBER/>
- BASQ: <https://github.com/ma921/SOBER/tree/main/SOBER/BASQ>
- BattINFO: <https://github.com/BIG-MAP/BattINFO>

Important note: the mentioned software has been developed outside of DigiBatt, however, further development, e.g. to extend functionalities or integration of the tools

with each other, will be conducted during project duration with personnel at least partially funded by DigiBatt. Whenever this is the case, acknowledgements to DigiBatt will be included in the next update.

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